

EFFECT OF FIBER CONCENTRATION AND PROCESS PARAMETERS ON FIBER ORIENTATION IN, AND MODULUS OF GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYETHYLENE COMPOSITE FIBER

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Abstract

This study is focused on delineating the effect of material, die, and process parameters on the orientation of short high aspect ratio glass fibers in polyethylene composite fiber extrudates. The effect of die entry angle, fiber weight fraction and screw speed on fiber orientation was systematically studied. The fiber orientation was characterized using X-ray tomography. The fiber orientation decreased with apparent viscosity of the melt in the die and the latter varied with die entry angle, screw speed, and fiber weight fraction in the feed.

1 Introduction

Orientation of short fibers in laminar flows has been investigated by many, theoretically and experimentally. In the classical theoretical study by Jeffery [1], the equations governing viscous (creeping) flow, around cylindrical particle in unbounded shear flow, were solved. Jeffery's results showed that most of the time, high-aspect-ratio cylindrical particle have their long axis nearly aligned in the plane of flow and spend only a small fraction of the time not so aligned. A subsequent theoretical work had employed slender body theory to derive similar results that apply to high-aspect-ratio cylinders, geometry more representative of a typical cylindrical fiber [2]. Strong fiber alignment is also induced in pure extensional flows. In this case, fibers approach perfect alignment of their long axis with the direction of flow on a timescale that is dictated by the strain rate imposed on the fluid.

Whether it is shear flow or extensional flow, high-aspect-ratio fibers tend to align themselves with the flow and it is this effect that underlies the flow-induced alignment techniques, which were studied by Mor et al. [2].

Fiber orientation during injection molding has been studied extensively [3, 4, 5, 6]; however, studies on fiber orientation during melt spinning are limited. Barbosa and Kenny [7] observed an increase in fiber orientation with increase in shear rate and decrease in fiber concentration. Vaxman and Narkis [8] recorded the opposite – a decrease in orientation with increase in shear rate. Their result on the effect of temperature was not conclusive. Becraft et al. [9] observed substantial fiber alignment even at very low level of shearing rate. The current study has expanded the scope of the previous studies by investigating the effect of additional parameters such as fiber volume fraction, die design and process parameters on fiber orientation and mechanical properties of the composite. Fiber Orientation Distribution (FOD) has been experimentally measured to aid in the analysis.

2 Experimental Details

High density Polyethylene (HDPE) and milled fiber glass were used in this study. The HDPE pellets were fed into Leistritz's co-rotating twin screw extruder. Fiber glass was fed through a side-stuffer after the polymer had completely melted. The

barrels were programmed to the following temperature (°C) profile: 232, 232, 232, 235, 235, 240, 240, 242, 242, 242, 242, and 242 (from the feed to die). The melt was extruded into composite fibers through a two-strand (3 mm in diameter with entry angles of 30°, 60°, and 90°) fiber die. The fiber weight fraction in the feed was varied between 10 – 50%. The extrudate was air-cooled to room temperature. Mechanical properties were measured using Instron’s screw driven universal testing machine. Density, measured as per ASTM D1895 - 96(2010)e1, was used to determine the volume fraction after extrusion. The orientation distribution of the glass fibers within the spun composite fiber was characterized non-destructively using X-radia’s Micro X-ray CT and Avizo’s Fire Software.

The reference coordinate system, used to define the orientation of a reinforcement fiber within the composite fiber, is provided in Fig. 1. The extrusion direction and the fiber’s longitudinal axis are oriented along the z-axis.

Figure 1 Coordinate reference system

The X-ray tomographic image was reconstructed using AVIZO Fire® software. A representative reconstructed image is shown in Fig 2.

Figure 2 X-ray image reconstructed using Avizo Fire® software.

A representative plot of FOD obtained by the analysis of the image in Fig.2, is provided in Fig.3. In order to aid in the interpretation, this FOD was used to determine a single orientation factor [11], defined by

$$f_a = [3 \langle \cos^2 \varphi \rangle - 1] / 2 \quad (6)$$

where

$$\langle \cos^2 \varphi \rangle = \int_0^{\pi/2} n_a(\varphi) \cos^2 \varphi \sin \varphi \quad (7)$$

Figure 3 FOD in the extrudate for various weight fractions of glass fibers in the feed

The orientation factor varies from 0 to 1.0 as the fiber distribution varies from random fiber orientation in 3-D to perfect alignment along the fiber axis.

3. Results and Discussion

The measured FOD in ϕ is plotted in Fig.3 for various weight fractions and 3 mm die with an entry angle of 60° . While a shift to lower angles (i.e. increase in orientation along the flow direction) with increase in weight fraction of fibers in the feed is observed, delineating the effect of various parameters is difficult. Therefore, a single orientation factor (f_a) was determined using eqn. (6) and used.

Fig.4 illustrates the variation of the orientation factor with weight fraction for various die entry angles. While the f_a varied the least for the 30° die, it varied significantly with fiber weight fraction in the feed for the 60° die. The variation for 90° die was in between that for 30° and 60° dies. The f_a was for 30°

was higher than that for other two dies, for all fiber weight fractions. While it decreased monotonically and marginally with increase in weight fractions for the 30° die, it showed a sinusoidal variation for other two dies. A minimum in f_a was observed at 30% weight fraction for 60° die. It is obvious from this figure that the effect of fiber weight fraction and die entry angle on f_a could not be delineated clearly. .

The die pressure increased with RPM as expected. The influence of die pressure on f_a is plotted in Fig. 5 for 60° die entry angle and fiber weight fraction in the feed of is 30%. Though, f_a appears not change with die pressure in Fig. 5, this trend is not very clear when considering other data. Similarly, the effect of shear rate, at the die exit (at the end of the cone) is not apparent in Fig. 6, for 60° die entry angle.

Finally, the apparent viscosity was determined assuming Newtonian behavior and is plotted as a function of f_a in Fig.7. It should be noted that these

data points correspond to a constant screw speed of 40 rpm. A clear trend is observed; the f_a decreased with increase in apparent viscosity.

The 30° die resulted in lowest viscosity and hence, highest fiber orientation. The 90° die resulted in highest viscosity and hence, lowest fiber orientation. The viscosity and fiber orientation for 60° were in between the values for the other two die angles, the

maximum scatter in data was observed for this die. The data points correspond to various fiber weight fractions in the feed. A sudden decrease in f_a at 30% weight fraction was observed for the 60° die. The reason for this is currently being investigated.

Figure 4 Orientation factor versus fiber weight fraction in the feed for die entry angles of 30°, 60°, and 30°

Figure 5 Orientation factor versus die pressure for

Figure 6 Orientation Factor as a function of shear rate

Figure 7 Orientation factor versus apparent viscosity for various die entry angles

Table 3 Mechanical properties

% W_f in Feed	Volume Fraction in Extrudate	Extrudate diameter (mm)	Orientation Factor	Measured Modulus (GPa)
10	0.09	1.7	0.82	2.72
20	0.03	1.5	0.80	3.16
30	0.11	1.9	0.75	6.00
40	0.37	1.9	0.79	15.99
50	0.30	1.8	0.86	14.99

The tensile modulus of the extrudates was measured and correlated with the f_a in support of the data presented above. The moduli for various extrudates obtained using a die with 90° entry angle and 1.5 mm diameter are tabulated in Table 1. These data correspond to a screw speed of 40 rpm.

The extrudates manufactured with a fiber weight fraction of 10% and 20% in the feed have modulus. However, the modulus of the extrudate manufactured with 30% weight fraction is twice that of 10 and 20% due to slightly higher volume fraction, despite the lower f_a . Similar conclusion can be drawn when properties of extrudates manufactured using fiber weight fraction of 40 % and 50% in the feed. It appears like the effect of volume fraction is more than that of f_a for the extrudates tested. Further investigation of this is underway.

Conclusion

Effect of die geometry, fiber weight fraction and screw speed on fiber orientation during extrusion of PE/Glass fiber composite was systematically studied. A clear effect of apparent viscosity on fiber orientation was observed; f_a decreased with increase in apparent viscosity. An increase in die angle increases the apparent viscosity, resulting in decrease in fiber orientation. The screw speed and the fiber weight fraction influence f_a through their

effect on apparent viscosity. The moduli of the extrudate correlate well with the f_a and fiber volume fraction in the extrudate.

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